

THREE-DIMENSIONAL STRESS ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE PLATES WITH OR WITHOUT STRESS CONCENTRATIONS

by

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ABSTRACT

Three-dimensional finite element analysis is used to reveal the state of stress at free edges of a simple composite plate, or of a composite plate with stress concentrations. The stress concentrations commonly encountered are: an open hole, a hole loaded by pin and a bolt-loaded hole. Examining the stress state in all these problems shows stress singularities at the ply interface between two layers of different ply orientation. The stress state depends on several factors such as material properties, laminate stacking sequence, problem geometry, and type of load application. The latter two factors, geometry and types of loading, are emphasized in this study. As an example of a geometric effect, some stress singularities that are present in the pin loaded hole configuration may not appear in the analysis of the free edge of a simple plate, even for identical ply orientation and material properties. As an example of a loading effect, bolt- and pin-loaded plates have different positions and magnitudes of stress singularities.

Locations of stress singularities are possible sites for failure initiation. The dependence of these stress singularities on geometry and types of loading indicates that suitable ply orientations for a simple plate may not be advisable for plates which contain stress concentrations.

1. INTRODUCTION

An early attempt to study the behavior of interlaminar stresses on the edge of a simple composite laminate, under uniform axial strain, has been done by Pipes and Pagano [1]. They applied a finite difference technique to obtain solutions for displacements and stresses. They showed there is a singularity in the interlaminar shear stresses of the interface and the free edge. Rybicki [2] used a three dimensional finite element technique based on the complementary energy formulation to obtain an approximate solution for the stresses of a finite symmetric laminate under inplane loading. Pipes and Daniel [3] applied the Moiré experimental technique to verify the form of the axial displacement field derived by Pipes and Pagano [1]. They also verified the boundary layer region in which the interlaminar edge effect is confined to be approximately equal to the laminate thickness. Wang and Crossman [4] utilized a generalized plane strain finite element procedure to investigate the stress field in symmetrically laminated composites of finite dimension. To avoid difficulties encountered in numerical methods, closed form theories were proposed by Pagano [5,6], Pipes and Pagano [7], Wang and Choi [8], and Kassapoglou and Lagace [9] to define the stress field of a composite laminate. Spilker and Chou [10] used a hybrid stress multilayer finite element and showed that there is no stress singularity near the free edge. To investigate the discrepancies in the results obtained by different authors in stress analysis of edge problem, Whitcomb *et. al* [11] used a finite element displacement method based on the total potential energy formulation to show the reliability of the finite element method to calculate free edge stresses in composite laminates. Also hybrid and singular hybrid finite element approaches have been used by Wang and Yuan [12-13] to study boundary layer stresses in composite laminates. In an attempt to study the edge effects and end effects on the interlaminar stress of angle ply laminates, Wei, and Zhao [14] utilized an eight-node linear finite element technique.

Most research in this field has been done for straight free edges, however there are some papers related to stress analysis of curved edges. Normal and interlaminar stresses around a hole in a composite plate have been studied by [15-22]. Stacking sequence, different lay-ups, and size effects on normal and interlaminar stresses near the edges have been considered in these studies.

Stress singularity analysis of pin and bolt loaded composite laminates are not considered sufficiently in the literature. Barboni *et. al* [23] studied the normal stress around the hole of a pin loaded composite laminate. By considering the importance of the three dimensional stress state for the pin and bolt loaded cases, this problem is still open for further research.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

2.1. The Simple Composite Plate

Consider a simple composite plate which has width W , length L , and thickness t (Fig. 1). The composite plate is subjected to a uniform strain ϵ_{xx} . The plate is a laminated composite consisting of several layers with different ply orientations. Each ply is assumed to be a transversely isotropic material and each ply has arbitrary ply orientation, but the laminate must be symmetric with respect to its mid-plane.

2.2 Composite Plate with a Pin or Bolt Loaded Hole

In this case, consider the composite plate with a pin or bolt loaded hole (Fig. 2). The plate has width w , length l , thickness t , edge distance e , hole diameter d , and washer diameter d_w . The plate is loaded through a pin or a bolt; pin load P , washer load P_w .

Each ply is assumed to be a transversely isotropic material and has arbitrary ply orientation but the laminate must be symmetric with respect to its mid plane. The AS4-3501-6 material simulated during stress analysis has the following material properties:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= 150. \text{ GPa} \\ E_{22} &= E_{33} = 8. \text{ GPa} \\ G_{12} &= G_{31} = 5. \text{ GPa} \\ G_{23} &= 3. \text{ GPa} \\ \nu_{12} &= \nu_{31} = \nu_{23} = .3 \end{aligned}$$

where the 1, 2, and 3 are on-axis directions.

3. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The stress analysis of all models was performed with SDRC I-DEAS finite element software [24]. Edge effects, delamination, out-of-plane buckling and stacking sequence effects are fully three dimensional phenomena. To study these phenomena and for analyzing the stresses along the free edge of the simple composite plate as well as the stresses in a pin or bolt loaded application, applying a three dimensional finite element technique is essential. To achieve high accuracy, the isoparametric quadratic 20-node brick element was used. In the following, the results of the three dimensional stress analysis for the simple composite plate, as well as the pin or bolt loaded composite plate are shown. Results have been obtained in all cases for cross-ply laminates, $[0/90]_s$ and $[90/0]_s$.

3.1 Slice Model Setup

To simulate the simple composite plate, different techniques can be used and a two dimensional generalized plane strain model is the most common choice. In this study a three dimensional 20-node brick element has been used in order to see all six stress components. To save runtime and memory a slice model was created by cutting out a thin slice from the composite plate (Fig. 1). The thin slice was modeled with the use of 2700 elements and 18000 nodes. In the areas with highest stress gradients the elements were concentrated, near the free edge (line A-B, Fig. 1) and between the plies (line C-D, Fig. 1). The stress analysis was performed for $[0/90]_s$, and $[90/0]_s$ ply lay-ups.

3.2 Slice Model Boundary Conditions

By considering symmetry with respect to the xy-plane and the zx-plane, one quarter of the slice is modeled in the finite element analysis (Fig. 1). To simulate a thin slice of a composite plate, all conjugate nodes along the x-axis were constrained to move equally in both the y and z directions. The constant strain was simulated by fixing all nodes on one side of the slice with respect to the x-direction, while all nodes on other side of the slice were induced with a constant tensile displacement. The model is one element "thick" along the x-axis.

3.3 Results of the Simple Composite Plate

The results of the stress analysis for both the $[0/90]_s$ and $[90/0]_s$ of the slice model are presented here. Due to the nature of the problem, both σ_{xy} and σ_{zx} are zero throughout the problem. In Fig. 3, σ_{zz} and σ_{yz} along line A-B (see Fig. 1) are sketched for both cross-ply laminates $[0/90]_s$ and $[90/0]_s$. By comparing both the σ_{zz} stresses and the σ_{yz} stresses, it is seen that the critical points for stress singularities are between the 0 and 90 degree plies, for both the $[0/90]_s$ and the $[90/0]_s$ configurations. The maximum positive normal stresses σ_{zz} for $[0/90]_s$ is higher than that for $[90/0]_s$. This indicates that $[90/0]_s$ is stronger than $[0/90]_s$ for resisting delamination. This evidence confirms the experimental results reported in [25], where it was found that lay-ups with 90° layers at the surface show superior bearing strength. The shearing stresses along the free edge are effectively negligible at all points except between adjacent 0 and 90 degree plies, whereas the normal stresses σ_{zz} have non-zero magnitudes along most of line A-B. Also, by comparing the normal stress σ_{zz} and the shear stress σ_{yz} , the interlaminar normal stresses are shown to be of the same order of magnitude as the interlaminar shear stresses. However, to determine which stresses are more significant, the effect of normal and shear stresses on delamination must be examined further with a suitable failure criterion.

The stresses between the plies along line C-D (see Fig. 1) are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 for the $[0/90]_s$ and the $[90/0]_s$ cases, respectively. The stresses σ_{zz} and σ_{yz} have singularities as the end is reached along line C-D (note that Figs. 4 and 5 only show the portion of line C-D nearest to the edge). Once again, this is an out-of-plane phenomenon that cannot be observed by classical laminated plate theory.

3.4 Pin and Bolt Loaded Model Setup

Three different finite element models were setup in an attempt to show the importance in element selection during finite element modeling. Models were created with $[0/90]_s$ and $[90/0]_s$ ply configurations with coarse, medium and fine meshes for bolt and pin loaded conditions. At first a coarse model with 162 brick elements and 1088 nodes was created. The coarse model did not incorporate a finer meshing near the stress singularities regions. Thereafter a medium mesh size was selected which increased the number of elements to 738 and nodes to 4078. Care was taken by increasing the number of elements near the hole edge. Finally, a third, fine mesh size was modeled, which once again increased the number of elements to 2400 and nodes to 8600. In the fine model, elements were concentrated around the hole, whereas far from the hole where less elements were required, the meshing remained coarse. By considering the symmetry of $[0/90]_s$ and $[90/0]_s$ pin or bolt loaded composite plates with respect to xy, and zx planes, one quarter of the specimen is modeled in the finite element analysis. The pin or bolt loaded plates are subjected to a far field applied stress of $\sigma_{xx} = 10$ MPa.

3.5 Pin and Bolt Loaded Boundary Conditions

To simulate the pin load, radial displacement boundary conditions have been applied on nodes around the hole at the load region (nodes from 0 to 82.5 degrees were restrained radially). Previous experience for the two dimensional case [26] shows that applying tangential boundary conditions to simulate friction between pin and hole induces an over constraint on the model, and provides unreliable results, therefore tangential boundary conditions around the hole were not used.

To simulate a fully tightened bolt, a uniform pressure was applied to the face of the composite plate under the washer region. Fixed displacement boundary conditions in the R and θ directions are also

applied on the nodes on the surface of this same region to simulate friction between the washer and the plate (Fig. 2).

3.6 Results for Pin Loaded Composite Laminates

The pin loaded case was studied to show the importance of element creation and selection during stress analysis. In Fig. 6, the all six stresses in cylindrical coordinate are shown for the $[0/90]_S$ pin loaded composite plate. Each of the six graphs contains three curves: coarse, medium, and fine models. The results show that the stresses vary with the chosen meshing. It is especially noticeable in σ_{ZZ} , σ_{XZ} , and σ_{YZ} , where the maximum stresses vary by a ratio of more than 3:1, fine to coarse results. Reliable results can therefore only be obtained when the proper element mesh is being applied.

Normal stresses σ_{ZZ} for $[90/0]_S$ configuration for coarse, medium, and fine models are presented in Fig. 7. The other stresses have been left out because they are exactly equal to those of the $[0/90]_S$ case. Once again the results show that only the fine pin loaded model can accurately demonstrate the behavior of the normal σ_{ZZ} stresses. As was the case for the simple plate, the magnitude of σ_{ZZ} stresses indicate that the $[90/0]_S$ is stronger than the $[0/90]_S$ configuration.

3.7 Results of the Bolt Loaded Composite Laminates

In Figs. 8 and 9, six different stresses for $[0/90]_S$ and $[90/0]_S$ under bolt loading conditions are shown respectively. Comparing with the pin loaded case, applying bolt load decreases all stresses dramatically. By comparing normal stress, σ_{ZZ} , and interlaminar shear stresses, σ_{ZR} and $\sigma_{\theta Z}$, in Figs. 6 and 7, it is concluded that applying bolt load can decrease the normal and interlaminar shear stresses of $[0/90]_S$ case more than $[90/0]_S$ case. The $[0/90]_S$ lay-up had a higher tensile σ_{ZZ} than $[90/0]_S$ in the pinned case, thus adding the bolt load is more beneficial to the $[0/90]_S$ case. If a comparison is made between Figs. 6 and 8, the $[0/90]_S$ case pinned versus bolted, the effect of the bolted washer dramatically decreases the interlaminar shear stresses, σ_{ZR} and $\sigma_{\theta Z}$. This result shows the effect of the frictional interface between the washer and the material, which may have a great influence on damage-causing interlaminar stresses.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present study shows the stress singularity analysis of a simple composite plate and a pin/bolt loaded composite laminate. A novel slice model is presented to simulate the simple composite plate using 20-node quadratic isoparametric element. A convergence study is performed to find the suitable mesh refinements for the stress analysis of a pin/bolt loaded composite laminate. Two different configurations, $[0/90]_S$ and $[90/0]_S$ are considered and compared. Results obtained for a simple composite laminates show there is no stress singularity for σ_{ZX} , however for a pin/bolt loaded composite laminates there are stress singularities for all interlaminar normal and shear stresses. This result shows the dependence of stress singularities on geometry and types of loading. Therefore a suitable ply orientation for a simple plate may not be advisable for plates which contain stress concentrations.

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Fig. 1 Simple composite plate, slice model

Fig. 2 Composite plate under pin/bolt load

Fig. 3 Simple composite plate, interlaminar stresses along line AB

Fig. 4 Simple composite plate, interlaminar stresses along line CD for [0/90]_s case (stresses plotted from point C to 0.1 w)

Fig. 5 Simple composite plate, interlaminar stresses along line CD for [90/0]s case (stresses plotted from point C to 0.1 w)

Fig. 6 Variation in stresses for the pin loaded [0/90]s case (coarse, medium and fine curves , stresses between 0 and 90 degree plies)

Fig. 7 Variation of Sigma-ZZ for the pin loaded [90/0]s case (coarse, medium and fine curves, stresses between 90 and 0 degree plies)

Fig. 8 Variation of stresses of a bolt loaded [0/90]s case
(between the 0 and 90 degree plies)

Fig. 9 Variation of stresses of a bolt loaded [90/0]s case
(between the 90 and 0 degree plies)